

Study of binary systems including mesophase and determination of latent transition temperature (LTT)

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Abstract : Six binary systems consisting of common component A₁ and A₂ (mesogen) are mixed with uncommon component (B) (nonmesogen), i.e. *para*-substituted Schiff's bases. The results shows that the mixed melt have the latent ability to exhibit mesomorphism. This latent transitions temperatures of nonliquid crystal substances are determined by the extrapolation method. The transition temperatures of the binary systems as well as the constituent components were observed through hot stage polarising microscope. LTTs determined are mutually comparable and well compared with others.

Keywords : Mixed mesomorphism, nematic, liquid crystal, mixed melt, mesogen.

Introduction

Non-mesogenic components of a binary system mixed with a liquid crystal component have the latent ability to exhibit mesomorphism. This latent transition temperature of non-mesogenic substances (B) are determined by the extrapolation method. Several binary systems have been studied earlier¹⁻⁵ with a view to understand the effect of terminal groups on liquid crystallinity in a mixed melt and to determine latent transition temperature of nonliquid crystal component. Present binary systems consisting of structurally similar components viz. 2-(4'-*n*-dodecyloxybenzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-2''-methoxybenzene [85.0°C Sm. - 103.0 °C - Nm - 122.0 °C Iso.] (A₁) and 4-(4'-*n*-decyloxybenzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-3''-chlorobenzene [104.0 °C Nm - 138.0 °C Iso.] (A₂) as mesogenic component and other as a non-mesogenic component (Schiff's base) (B) with general formula X-C₆H₄-CH=N-C₆H₄-Y, where X = -Cl, -CH₃; Y = -OC₂H₅, -CH₃ groups are studied to determine LTT of non-mesogenic component by extrapolation method.

Experimental

Preparation of components A₁ and A₂ :

Components (A₁) 2-(4'-*n*-dodecyloxybenzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-2''-methoxybenzene and component (A₂) 4-(4'-*n*-decyloxybenzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-3''-chlorobenzene were prepared by established method⁶⁻⁹.

Preparation of components B₁, B₂ and B₃ :

Component (B₁) *p*-chlorobenzal-*p'*-phenitidine, (B₂) *p*-chlorobenzal-*p'*-toluidine and (B₃) *p*-tolual-*p'*-phenitidine were synthesized by refluxing appropriate aldehyde and amine in alcohol for two hours¹⁰ in equimolar proportion. Products were washed and crystallized by alcohol, till their constant melting points are obtained.

Table 1. Component (A₁) 2-(4'-dodecyloxybenzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-2''-methoxybenzene and component (A₂) 4-(4'-decyloxybenzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-3''-chlorobenzenes, mixed with component (B) Schiff's base

Schiff's base	X	Y	M.p. (°C)
B ₁	-Cl	-OC ₂ H ₅	121.5
B ₂	-Cl	-CH ₃	128.0
B ₃	-CH ₃	-OC ₂ H ₅	108.5

Preparation of binary mixtures :

Binary mixtures of systems were prepared by weighing accurately constituent components. Compounds of mixtures were thoroughly mixed, so as to get homologous mass of a sample by usual established method¹⁰. Samples of binary mixtures were observed through hot stage polarising microscope as shown in the phase diagrams (Figs. 1 to 6).

Results and discussion

Six binary systems under investigation are recorded in Table 1. The transition temperatures of pure components and binary mixtures as well as mole% and temperatures of eutectic point and triple point as derived from phase diagram are recorded in Table 2.

Sl. no.	Schiff's base (B) mixed with component A ₁		Range of composition over which mesophase appears in terms of mole% A ₁
	-X	-Y	
1.	-Cl	-OC ₂ H ₅	31.4 to 100.0 (Nematic)
2.	-Cl	-CH ₃	28.5 to 100.0 (Nematic)
3.	-CH ₃	-OC ₂ H ₅	49.0 to 100.0 (Nematic)
	Schiff's base (B) mixed with component A ₂		Range of composition over which mesophase appears in terms of mole% A ₂
	-X	-Y	
4.	-Cl	-OC ₂ H ₅	33.0 to 100.0 (Nematic)
5.	-Cl	-CH ₃	30.3 to 100.0 (Nematic)
6.	-CH ₃	-OC ₂ H ₅	40.5 to 100.0 (Nematic)

The geometry of the molecules of binary systems are similar in shape, size and with respect to aromaticity. The variation in the polarity of the terminal groups causes variation in the mesomorphic characteristics. In present discussion the constituent components of the binary mixtures are structurally identical and component A₁ and A₂ has sufficient polar terminal group rising to terminal attraction in ample measure. Hence on heating the binary mixture of varying composition, they form nematic mesophase because terminal attractions offer resistance to thermal vibration maintaining an end to end alignment over a range of temperature. Thus considerable cohesive intermolecular forces of attractions conducive to mesophase formation operate over wide range of composition as shown in Table 3.

Binary system no.	Schiff's base		LTT			
	X-Ph-Ch=N-Ph-Y	-X	-Y	Present Study		
				(A ₁)	(A ₂)	Lohar and Mashru (Ref. 11)
B ₁	-Cl	-OC ₂ H ₅	74.0 (Nm)	92.0 (Nm)	79.0	86.0
B ₂	-Cl	-CH ₃	98.0 (Nm)	108.0 (Nm)	-	-
B ₃	-CH ₃	-OC ₂ H ₅	84.0 (Nm)	102.0 (Nm)	-	90.0

The admixed molecule disturbs the packing of component (A) resulting into depression of elevation of

transition temperature depending upon the type of polar end groups. The disturbances caused by nonliquid crystal component, the range of mixed mesophase formation and degree of exhibition depends upon the efficiency of non-mesogenic component (B) to affect the molecular alignment of component (A₁) and (A₂) in a mixed melt depending upon end to end attractions. The minimum composition needed to disrupt completely the mesomorphic alignment of component A₁ and A₂ depends upon the polarity of the terminal end groups of component (B). In binary system 1, 2 and 4, 5 have -Cl as common left terminal for component (B) with varying right terminal -OC₂H₅ and -CH₃ respectively. In binary systems 3 and 6 have common -CH₃ and -OC₂H₅ as left and right terminals respectively. Above all left and right terminals are relatively more polar than any other terminal groups. Therefore they are causing strong intermolecular forces of attractions which are capable of maintaining parallel orientational order of molecules, resulting into nematogenic mesophase formation in mixed melt. This resulted to maintain nematic mesophase formation up to 68.6, 71.5, 50.5, 67.0, 69.7 and 59.5 mole% of (B) for binary systems 1 to 6 respectively. Thereafter mesomorphic alignment of compound A₁ and A₂ are not maintained. Thus polarity and hence the intermolecular forces of attractions caused by terminal groups due to component (B) fails to maintain parallel orientational order of molecules in a mixed melt due to shortage of enough intermolecular attractions. Therefore it proves that, if any one or both terminally linked end groups are strongly dipolar, the 'additive effect' i.e. combined effect of both end groups does play the role to maintain statically ordered parallel orientations of the molecules to exhibit nematic mesophase formation in a mixed melt.

The mole% of component (A) are plotted against the transition temperatures which are represented in Figs. 1 to 6. From the phase diagram Figs. 1 to 6 of the binary systems, it is observed that enantiotropic nematic mesophase appears within certain range of composition and temperature of the component A₁ and A₂.

In Figs. 1 and 4 the nematic-isotropic transition curve meet melting point curve to the left of the eutectic point (67.0 °C and 80.0 °C) respectively. As a result wide range of nematic mesophase occurs in mixed melt. The range of composition required in terms of mole% of A₁ and A₂ is 31.4 to 100 in binary system-1 and 33.0 to 100.0 in binary

Fig. 1. Phase diagram of the system 2-(4'-*n*-dodecyloxybenzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-2''-methoxybenzene and *p*-chlorobenzal-*p*'-phenitidine (A₁ + B₁).

system-4. On extrapolating the mesophase-isotropic transition curve to zero mole% of A₁ and A₂, so as to determine latent transition temperature at 74.0 °C in binary system-1 and 92.0 °C for respectively Schiff's base in binary system-4 which is below the melting point of component (B).

In Figs. 2 and 5 same way as earlier the mesomorphic-isotropic transition curve meet melting point curve to the left of the eutectic point at 67.0 °C in case of binary system-2 and at 82.0 °C for binary system -5. Component B contain less polar group -Cl and -CH₃ and relatively higher melting point in case of binary system-2. As a result the mesomorphic range is slightly higher as compared to binary systems-1, 3, 4 and 6. Therefore mole% of B required for disrupting the mesomorphic alignment of component A₁

and A₂ is 71.5 mole% in binary system-2 and 69.7 mole% in binary system-5. On extrapolating the nematic-isotropic transition curve to the zero mole% of component A₁ and A₂, the latent transition temperature occurs at 98.0 °C in binary system-2 and 108.0 °C in binary system-5.

Similarly in Figs. 3 and 6 the mesomorphic transition curve meet melting point curve to the left of the eutectic point at 60.0 °C in binary system-3 and 40.0 °C in binary system-6. It also shows wide range of mesophase due to higher combined polarity of terminal groups -CH₃ and -OC₂H₅ in component B. Mesophase is appeared at 73.0 °C in binary system-3 and 82.0 °C in binary system-6 thus required mole% of A₁ is 49.0 and mole% of A₂ is 40.5. Extrapolating the mesomorphic-isotropic transition curve the latent transition temperature occurs at 84.0 °C

Fig. 2. Phase diagram of the system 2-(4'-*n*-dodecyloxybenzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-2''-methoxybenzene and *p*-chlorobenzal-*p*'-toluidine (A₁ + B₂).

Fig. 3. Phase diagram of the system 2-(4'-*n*-dodecyloxybenzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-2''-methoxybenzene and *p*-tolual-*p*'-phenitidine ($A_1 + B_3$).

in binary system-3 and 102.0 °C in binary system-6.

The effect of the central group is negligible to the mesophase formation in all binary systems. Therefore range of composition over which mesophase appeared in mixed melt depend upon terminal group $-OC_2H_5$, $-CH_3$ and $-Cl$ respectively.

Thus extrapolation could be quite dependable when non-mesomorphic substances are structurally similar to mesomorphic substances and possess sufficiently polar terminal groups. In all binary systems studied, the isotropic liquid could be super cooled to the mesophase and hence extrapolation is easily achieved. The mesomorphic-isotropic

transition curve, of all binary systems has been extrapolated with smoothness of the transition curve. The extrapolation of such curves yields of latent transition values (LTT's) (Table 4) for Schiff's bases. All the values of LTT determined are comparable with previous work, as these Schiff's bases possess sufficiently polar end groups. In the phase diagram of all the binary systems melting point curves meet to the left of the respective eutectic points. Therefore eutectic points of systems 1 to 6 are in equilibrium with nematic liquid phase. Thus it can be concluded that, higher the polarity of the terminal group, more is the probability of mesomorphic-isotropic transition curve to meet the solid-isotropic transition curve to the

Fig. 4. Phase diagram of the system 4-(4'-*n*-dodecyloxybenzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-3''-chlorobenzene and *p*-chlorobenzal-*p*'-phenitidine ($A_2 + B_1$).

Fig. 5. Phase diagram of the system 4-(4'-*n*-decyloxybenzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-3''-chlorobenzene and *p*-chlorobenzal-*p*'-toluidine (A₂ + B₂).

Fig. 6. Phase diagram of the system 4-(4'-*n*-dodecyloxybenzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-3''-chlorobenzene and *p*-tolual-*p*'-phenitidine (A₂ + B₃).

left of the eutectic point. This probability can be linked with the probability of the extrapolation of mesomorphic-isotropic transition curve.

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